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Influence of Gender and Location Norms on Academic Corruption among Senior Secondary School Students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was to determine the influence of gender and location norms of the academic corruption among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. An instrumentation research design was adopted. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class three (SSIII) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Bayelsa State. A sample size of 500 students consisting of 250 males and 250 females, were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Data were obtained with the standardized academic-corruption -sensitivity-test (ACST) instrument which was validated through face, content and construct validity which gave a construct validity coefficients of .56, .86 and .90 as well as its reliability was determined through Cronbach alpha which gives a reliability coefficient of .89. Data were analyzed with percentiles ranking and stanine while the two null hypotheses were tested with t-test at .05 level of significance. It was observed that there is no statistically significant difference between male and female students on academic corruption while there was significant difference between rural and urban students on academic corruption. The ACST norms ranged from 0-100% indicating from very highly corrupt to not very corrupt. The study therefore concludes that male and female students have similar vulnerability to academic corruption while rural students have higher susceptibility to academic corruption than urban students. Based on these conclusions, the study further recommends that the ACST scale should be used alongside with aptitude test for admissions in order to identify corrupt candidates and refer them for counselling services before admissions.

Keywords: Academic corruption, norms, location, sensitivity, gender and test

Introduction

Corruption has become a household name in Nigeria. Corruption seems unabated and had entered into the bone marrow of individuals whose conscience are no more alive. Corruption has bedeviled the nation to the point that each successive government became vulnerable to it. Though, conceptualization of corruption poses no debate among intellectuals, particularly social scientists. Only that definitions advanced accordingly from one situation or country to another depending on deviations from prescribed patterns of bureaucratic behaviour. Ganner (1999, p.348) defined corruption as the act of doing something with an intent to give some advantage inconsistent with official duty and the rights of others, a fiduciary's or official's use of a station or office to procure some benefit either personally or for someone else, contrary to the rights of others. This definition relates corruption as any act that deviates from moral and ethical sets of behaviour. Meanwhile Obansajo (2000, p.4) stated that "we realized that corruption covers a wide spectrum of acts and not just the simple act of giving and receiving of bribes". Furthermore, corruption covers such acts as use of one's office for pecuniary advantage, gratification, influence peddling, and insincerity in advice with aim of gaining advantage, less than a full day's work for a full day's pay and tardiness and slovenliness, Obasanjo (2000) remarked. This could make one to describe corruption as any act of deviation from formal rules that regulate behaviour of individuals in any given society or organization.

From this point of view corruption can be said to be a complex and multi-faceted phenomenon with multiple causes and effects. It is not a misnomer to conclude that corruption is any act of violating regulations or wrong doing in whatever form to achieve success either personally or for someone else contrary to the rights of others. It is the act of unethical practices in schools. This ugly hydraheaded problem had crept into the educational sectors especially the secondary sector where miracle centers are provided for examination malpractices. The study, therefore, conceptualizes academic corruption as act of deviation by students from formal rules that regulate their behaviours in the secondary education system.

Against this backdrop, academic performance of students are reported in letter grade or grade point average terms, such reporting focuses on the basis of tests and examination of learning outcomes in the cognitive domain, affective and psychomotor domains. However, in practical terms, considerably less, if not no focus on the affective and psychomotor domains in academic achievement of students. Whatever form it takes, academic corruption such as grade inflation, examination

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malpractices, cheating, bribery, exchange of grade for sex, cultism and so on has a deleterious effect on the academic achievement of students. This unabated trend can plunge the educational system to breed a rising tide of educational mediocrity. Natia (2004, p.3) arguably viewed that corruption leads to:

Educational inefficiency. It impairs the quality of the education students receive. It destroys the concepts of meritocracy and honest academic achievement. It leads to frustration and damages the morale of students and faculty. It weakens public trust in the process and products of the university and academic enterprises and reduces the value of degrees.

It is crystal clear that corruption not only affects academic achievement of students but destroys several academic glories including character and ethics. It is a social and economic cancer. It could be acknowledged that academic corruption in the forms of bribery, forgery, falsification of examination results, patronage, cronyism, examination malpractices, cultism, destruction of school property, etc. deteriorate the quality of the secondary education thereby producing not just low but smoke-screen academic performance of students. Opalaye (2005) reported that secondary school education is like a window through which students peep out to see which direction he/she wants to go. It is so frustrating that miracle examination centers have been put in place where students will leave their schools and go to and register for their SSC examinations. These candidates after making their papers would write JAMB and consequently admitted into the tertiary education and could not defend their papers anymore.

Uzoagba and Keke (2017) asserted that education is a living thing successful only if it is inspired by the cultural foundations of the people whom it seeks to serve. The paper concluded that corruption in education threatens equality and quality of its beneficiaries. There are tremendous effects corruption impose on education. One of them is the production of half-baked graduates that could not defend themselves in any field of human endeavour and at the same time cannot contribute to nation building. Another significant effect of corruption in education is its ability to discourage hard work, honesty and other moral virtues among students rather they promote vices such as indiscipline of all kinds (Uzoagba & Keke, 2017). Madaki (2019) stated that students and parents systematically and shamelessly impact the education sector incentives, unmerited gifts, donations to the school in order to influence decisions regarding their children and wards. These unethical behaviours can only be elicited or inferred by using a non-cognitive test such as the academic corruption sensitivity test (ACST).

From this backdrop, it became necessary to determine the gender and location norms from the ACST to enable valid interpretation and comparison across gender and geographic location of students. Norms are very important tools used to provide reliable information about the test taker as well as enable the comparison of students who at anytime take the test with standardization sample, remarked Ughamadu et al., (1991). Onunkwo (2005) asserted that norms are standards based on which judgements or decisions are made. To this end, identifying norms of gender and location of schools for the ACST instrument became instructive in order to make valued judgement or decision at anytime the ACST is being put into use. Norms are average scores such as mean or standard scores such as T-score, Z-score, percentile rank, Stanine, etc. This study made use of stannine and percentile ranks to determine the gender based and geographic location-based norms.

There are plethora of psychological tests that measures cognitive traits of students. The academic corruption sensitivity test (ACST) is a non-cognitive scale standardized to elicit academic related traits from learners in secondary school in Bayelsa State. The scale has 30 items structured in the likert format with a 5-point continuum. The ACST is valid and reliable however gender and location-based norms have not been determined. The absence of these norms can make the interpretation of the scale difficult. Meanwhile, the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2020) determines gender norms as a subset of social norms that relate specifically to gender differences. This relates that gender norms are social principles that control the behaviour of males and females in society and restrict their gender identity into what is considered to be appropriate while location norms are part of the social norms that identify rural and urban differences which are fundamental to planning and formulation of policy especially in the educational sector. Identifying these gender and location based norms for the ACST will help in the utility of the instruments regarding rendering counseling services, control gender based behaviors, planning and formulation of policies in curbing academic corruption among secondary school system and educational system at large. Therefore, this study was to determine the gender and location norms of the ACST among secondary school students in Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Research Problem

Education in Nigeria is considered as a vital instrument for effecting national development. It has been structured in a way the philosophy and desirable objectives of the nation would be achieved through the educational system. It portends quality and effective education that is free from corruption, development of the individual into a sound and effective citizen,

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and provision of equal access to educational opportunities for all citizens of the country at primary, secondary and tertiary levels (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004). However, it has been observed that corruption has bedeviled the educational system in the form of examination malpractices, cultism, hooliganism, sex-for-grade, and so on. (Sakwa & Abdullahi, 2023) asserted that problem of academic corruption (examination malpractices) has remain unabated and spread to all educational levels with candidates taking senior secondary school certificate examination (SSCE) championing the crusade. This becomes alarming that if not tackle empirically can plunged the educational system to breed half-baked graduates without feet, hooligans, cultists, etc. Even, the standard of education will be inexplicably fallen in Bayelsa State and Nigeria at large. It became necessary therefore for this study to examine the influence of gender and school location norms on academic corruption among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The following objectives were posed to guide the study. The study was to:

1. determine the norms of Academic Corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State.
2. establish gender norms of Academic Corruption among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State
3. determine location of school norms on Academic Corruption among students in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study. These include:

- i. What are the norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?
- ii. What are the male and female norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?
- iii. What are the location norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance to make decisions on the variables being investigated.

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students’ academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Ho2: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of rural and urban students academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Methodology

This study adopted an instrumentation research design which enabled the researcher to adopt the standardized Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) to collect gender-based and locatio-based data for content and statistical analysis. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class three (SSIII) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Bayelsa State. A sample size of 500 students consisting of 250 males and 250 females as well as of the divide of 292 and 209 rural and urban students respectively, were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test was constructed and standardized by Queensoap (2006). The ACST followed necessary procedures for the standardization of a non-cognitive test. The ACST was validated through face, content and construct validity which gave a construct validity coefficients of .56, .86 and .90 for Negative Item Scores (NIS) vs Positive Item Scores (PIS), Negative Item Score (NIS) vs Total Item Scores (TIS) and Positive Item Scores (PIS) vs Total Item Scores (TIS) respectively as well as its reliability was determined through Cronbach alpha which gives a reliability coefficient of .89. The researcher recruited research assistants to help administer the study instrument to respondents after securing ethical approval from relevant authorities. Data obtained were analyzed using percentile ranking, stanine and t-test.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What are the norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Computation of Percentile Ranks for the ACST Norms

ACST Scores	Percentile Ranks	Stanine	Norms Intepretation
131-150	81 – 100	9, 8, 7 and 6	Very Honest (not very corrupt)
122-130	61 – 80	5, 4, and 3	Honest (not corrupt)
111-121	41 – 60	2	Moderately corrupt
99-110	21 – 40	1	Highly corrupt

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Below 99	0 – 20	1	Very highly corrupt
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Source: Field Work

Table 1 indicated the norms of the Academic Corruption Sensitivity Test (ACST) administered to 500 secondary school students. It can be discerned from table 1 that very honest (not very corrupt) students has a norm range of 81-100, honest (not corrupt) students has 61-80, moderately corrupt students was 41-60, highly corrupt students was 21-40 and very highly corrupt was 0-20 with the corresponding scores of ACST as 131-150, 122-130, 111-121, 99-110 and below 99 respectively. Table 1 also showed the stanine equivalents of the norms. This implies that ACST scores can be converted to stanines and help interpret the extent of corrupt act of students. Again, it can be deduced from Table 1 that 51% of students' score lie below 117 while 74% and 24% of the students' scores lie below the upper quartile and lower quartile respectively. This implies that 74% of the students lie the upper quartile score 128 while 24% was observed lying below the first quartile score, 101.

Research Question 2

What are the male and female norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Summary of Computation of Gender Norms using Stanines

Variables	Stanines /percentile norms (%)								
	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
Male (N = 250)	96+	90-95	84-89	79-83	73-78	67-72	61-66	55-65	Below 55
Female (N = 250)	96+	90-95	85-89	79-84	73-78	67-72	61-66	55-65	Below 55

Source: Field Work

Table 2 showed the various stanines for male and female students who responded the ACST scale. It was observed that male and female students who scored 96% and above were assigned stanine 9 while male and female students who scored 90%-95% were assigned stanine 8. Stanine 7 was assigned to male and female students who scored 84% - 89% and 85% - 89% respectively while both male and female students who scored 73%-78%, 67%-72%, 61%-66%, 55%-60% and below 55% were assigned stanines 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. This implies that male level of academic corruption does not differ from female students' level of academic corruption. They barely had the same norms as measured with stanine 9.

Research Question 3

What are the location norms of academic corruption among secondary school students in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Summary of computation of school location norms using Stanines

Variables	Stanines /percentile norms (%)								
	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
Rural (N = 292)	94+	89 -93	83 – 88	77-82	71- 76	65-70	59-64	53-58	Below 53
Urban (N = 208)	97+	92 -96	87 – 91	81-86	76-80	71-75	65-70	60-64	Below 60

Source: Field Work

Table 3 showed the school location norms. It was found that in urban schools stanine 9 was assigned to a student score of 97% and above. For rural school location stanine 9 was assigned to students who scored 94% and above. Also, it was observed that students in urban who scored 65%-70% were assigned with stanine 3 while in rural location students who scored 65% - 70% were assigned with stanine 4. Stanine 1 was assigned to students who scored below 60% and 53% in urban and rural locations respectively. This implies that academic corruption levels differ from school locations. It means school locations influences academic corruption. This was evidenced of the fact that their stanine placements were not the same.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students' academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Table 4: Summary of t-test statistics for the difference between the mean-scores of male and female students as measured in the ACST

Unpaired variables	N	Mean	Sd	T	Df	P val	95% CI	P < .05?	Decision
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Influence of Gender and ... (Queensoap, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15079811>

Male	250	75	13	0.97	498	.33	-1.13 to 3.34	No	Not sig.
Female	250	76	12						H ₀ not rejected

Source: Field Work

The data in table 4 showed that male students has 250 participants, 75±13 mean and standard deviation while female students has 250 participants, 76±12 mean and standard deviation. It can be discerned from Table 4 that for t is 0.97, degree of freedom of 498, *P value* .33, 95% confidence interval of -1.13 to 3.34. This implies that *P value of* .33 is greater than chosen alpha of .05 thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students' academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State is not rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of rural and urban students academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Table 5: Summary of t-test statistics for the difference between the mean-scores of rural and urban students as measured in the ACST

Unpaired variables	N	Mean	Sd	T	Df	P val	95% CI	P < .05?	Decision
Rural	292	74	12	3.88	498	.0001	2.04 to 6.33	Yes	Sig.
Urban	208	78	12						H ₀ rejected

Table 5 depicted that rural location students has 292 participants, 74±12 mean and standard deviation while urban location students has 208 participants with 78±12 mean and standard deviation. This suggests that urban students seem more honest than the rural-located students because the mean for the former was greater than the later. It was also observed from table 5 that t is 3.88, degree of freedom is 498, *P value of* .0001, 95% confidence interval of 2.04 to 6.33. This denotes that *P value* (.0001) is less than the chosen alpha of *P* = .05 hence t no significant difference between the mean scores of rural and urban students academic corrupt practices among secondary schools in Bayelsa State was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The results supports Galtung (2005) which maintained that the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) ranks countries on a scale from zero to 10, using percentile matching and a score of ten represents a totally honest country while zero indicates a very corrupt country. This denotes that gender is not a factor that would influence academic corruption, male and female students are vulnerable to academic corruption and their corrupt practices are alike. In another study, though on corruption, observed significant disparity between male and female in corrupt practices, especially collection and giving of bribe. The study reveals that the disparity becomes even larger when factoring in the urban/rural dimension which informs that women living in rural areas are those least likely to pay bribes (21.6%) whereas men living in urban areas are most likely (39.3%), remarked (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2019).

This means that the extent of academic corruption differ significantly among students of post-primary school which is probably influenced by the location of the school. Since the mean of the urban students was greater than the rula-based students, it can be interpreted that urban-based students are less corrupt than rural-based students. In otherwords, urban-based students were more honest that the rural-based students. The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2019) reported that the decrease of the prevalence of corrupt acts in relation to customs/immigration officers, judges/magistrates, and police officers was particularly significant in rural areas, but less in urban areas. This suggests that location of school can influence corrupt acts of individual so far as other factors remain the same.

Conclusion

The study concludes that gender was not a factor in academic corruption. The ACST scores were tested at at .05 alpha significance level and the null hypothesis was accepted indicating that the norms of the scale for male and female has no statistically significant difference. It was also concluded that location of school was observed as a significant factor in academic corruption among secondary school students. The norms of the ACST were ranged from 0-100 %, indicating from very highly corrupt (0-20%) to not very corrupt (very honest) (81-100%). The findings of the study would help identify unethical behaviour and immoral acts to seek for measures to correct such corrupt acts which is to be implaicated for psychologists, guidance

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counsellor, psychometricians and sociologists in rendering their services to the students. Evaluation bodies such as National Examination Council (NECO) and West African School Examination Council (WAEC) would be implied with the findings because the findings might enable them modify their ways of setting or supervision of their examinations.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. The ACST norms should be used to identify and categorize students who are very highly corrupt to students who are very honest before admission into higher institutions. This will help refer academically corrupt students to institution counselling centre for behavioral modelling.
2. The gender based norms of the ACST be used to ensure gender balance for admission and placement purposes in educational system.
3. The geographic location norms of the ACST be adapted into planning and supply of school equipment, materials and supervision of examinations in rural and urban locations.

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